

Received: 28th August 2021

Revised: 15th October 2021

Accepted: 30th November 2021

An Investigation of Friction Co-Efficient between Piston Ring and Piston Cylinder Wall using Different Engine Oils

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ABSTRACT

The power outputs of modern reciprocating internal combustion engines have shown an increasing trend during the last decades. This higher power output associated with an increase in the speed of engines is proportional to a sharp rise in mechanical friction between the engine components in contact with each other's, leading to wear and an important loss of efficiency. It has been found that nearly 40 to 50 per cent of the frictional losses are due to the piston ring assembly only. Scientific knowledge of basic theory and design of internal combustion engine needs to reduce losses at critical parts, such as Piston Ring Assembly (PRA). The contribution of TOP ring in PRA systems has been computed with different operational parameters like speed and Lubrication. Effects of Lubrication and friction in piston rings are significantly attracting the researcher for a long time. In present work segment of piston ring and cylinder liner is considered for experimental work and try to find effect of different Engine Oil on Friction Co-efficient. At lower speed and high temperature co-efficient of friction observed major difference in all the oils. Obtained results are compiled on variation of lubricants found in good agreement with the published literature. Correct selection of lubricant Oil gives an effective result on engine performance.

Keywords: Co-efficient of friction, Viscosity, Lubrication Oil

Nomenclature

μ = coefficient of friction

F = friction force

N = normal force

mg = mass of body

F_{load} = applied load

τ = shear stress

A = contact area

μ = Kinematic viscosity in centistokes.

t = Time in seconds

1. INTRODUCTION

I.C. Engine invented many years back. In those years, numbers of changes occur and it will be continuing for improvement. Problem coming today is from the global warming and shortage of conventional fuel. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the fuel efficiency by decreasing various losses inside the engine. Engine designer and tribology engineers are

constantly challenging to innovative advance products to meet more demanding emissions and fuel economy targets. Current research and development on engine cylinder components includes new designs, materials, coating, and surface treatments, with goals of reduced weight, longer life, higher operating temperatures and reduced friction losses. Quantitative estimation of friction losses in initial design stages of an I.C. engine is a crucial factor that determines the fuel economy and performance of automobile.

1.1 Source of Friction in Modern Internal Combustion Engine:

Around 40-55% of total friction losses in an engine are attributed to the piston assembly friction, 20-30% to loaded bearings, 10-15% to valve train, whereas 15-25% is due to engine auxiliary losses.

Fig.1.1 Total energy in a fired engine

Fig.1.2 Total engine mechanical friction

Fig.1.3 Piston/ ring/ rod friction

Fig.1.4 Ring pack friction

Engine friction losses comprise from fig. 1.1, 1.2, 1.3 & 1.4, (1) Mechanical friction, (2) Accessories work (oil-, water-, fuel pumps, alternators, gears, etc.). In addition, pumping losses are accounted for in the engine bmep by adding both closed and open parts work and not in the frictional losses.

Mechanical friction observed in I.C. engine mainly in three different area like,

- Piston assembly, consisting of compression and oil rings, and piston skirt
- Valve train
- Crankshaft and connecting rod bearing [1].

The power cylinder accounts for 40-55 percent of total mechanical losses, with friction caused by the piston rings and cylinder liner accounting for half of those losses. In this case, friction effect on piston ring gives opportunity to improve engine efficiency, lower the fuel consumption and reduce emission. These are important objectives for present's

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automobile engine manufacturers, who are focusing to improve performance and satisfy ever-increasingly rigorous emission regulations [2].

1.2 Piston Ring and Liner system:

Piston rings of reciprocating engines have several functions; the important one from them is sealing the clearance between the piston and cylinder in order to retain gas pressure and to minimize blow-by. To guarantee that enough lubricant is applied to the cylinder surface to support high thrust and gas force loads at high speeds while keeping oil consumption under control. To keep piston surface temperatures relatively low while transferring heat from cylinder walls and coolant [3].

Fig. 1.5 Typical piston ring pack

In an internal combustion engine, the piston ring pack mainly consists of three radial rings located in a piston groove as shown in Fig.1.5. During engine operation, all such rings move together with the piston along the cylinder liner. To reduce significant power losses lubrication between ring and liner is needed. Another primary goal of the piston rings is to effectively distribute lubricant along the ring-width interface while preventing excessive oil from passing through the interface and leaking into the combustion chamber, where it could be consumed.

2. Friction:

A force that resists the relative motion or tendency to such motion of two bodies in contact, which is experienced whenever one solid body moves tangentially over another with which it is in contact.

2.1 Types of Friction:

Sliding Friction one-object slides against the surface of another object. i.e., Motion of piston in cylinder, Motion of plunger etc. *Rolling Friction* is the resistance to motion, which occurs when an object is role over a surface. i.e., Ball rolling inside ball bearing. Tire rolling on road etc. If one surface is moved relative to each other, the number of hilly points will come in contact and will resist motion (called Friction). Points of contact will become heated and sometimes these points will try to weld together. To reduce the resistance between surface-to-surface contacts, lubricating oil is essential to maintaining the space between the surfaces. Lubricating oil field the solid surfaces, and when one surface moves relative to the other, oil is dragged along with the surface. The oil separates the surfaces, and one surface hydraulically floats on the other. The shearing of fluid layers is only the resistance between relative motions, which is orders of magnitude less than that of dry surface motion [4].

2.2 Co-efficient of friction:

The coefficient of friction μ is defined as the ratio of the friction force F and the normal force N between the bodies, as expressed by

$$\mu = \frac{F}{N} \quad (1)$$

Where, the normal force is calculated from the sum of the load of the mass (mg) and any externally applied load (F_{load}),

$$N = mg + F_{load} \quad (2)$$

The normal force and contact area most probably perpendicular to each other. When moving the mass the friction force is the force which required to continuing movement and it always acts tangential (i.e. parallel) to the contact area [5].

The Friction co-efficient is calculated by known or experimental forces.

In moving body where the surfaces are fully separated by lubrication the friction force is simply expressed by

$$F = \tau A \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2.1 Illustration of shear forces between solid bodies and fluid in a lubricated contact

Where, τ is the shear stress in the lubrication regime and A is the area of contact. The shear stress is determined by the different lubricant properties, the speed of motion and the distance between the two bodies [6],[7],[8]. The forces between the two solid bodies and the fluid space, as shown in Figure 2.1

3. Experimental Procedure:

Table 3.1: Standard commercial Lubricant

Sr. No.	Name of Lubricants	CODE
1	MOBILE SAE 40	A
2	CASTROL SAE 20W 40	B
3	HONDA 10W 30	C

Table 3.1 shows the different standard commercial lubricants which one used for the experiment work [9],[10],[11]. An experiment starts with selection of currently used engine oil and measured its viscosity using Red viscometer.

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$$\mu = 0.26 \times t - \frac{171}{t} \tag{3}$$

Where,

μ = Kinematic viscosity in centistokes.

t= Time in seconds to collect 50ml. of oil.

Fig 3.1 Temperature v/s Viscosity- comparison of oils

Fig. 3.1 indicates the comparison of three oils, SAE 20W 40 oil have a low viscosity as compare to other two oils between 30-to-55-degree temperatures. It has clearly shown that the viscosity of oil SAE 20W 40 decreased with respect to temperature but it is slightly higher than other two oils.

3.1 Reciprocating Test Rig:

Experimental co-efficient of friction measured on available test-rig under different operating conditions [12]. The approximated half piston ring segment fitted on piston block in such a way to maintaining actual ring clearance at the groove of piston. As shown in fig. 3.2. The reciprocating test rig is used for evaluated coefficient friction, temperature and normal force acting between the segmented ring liner of I.C. engine.

Fig. 3.2 Enlarged view of test setup.

The Specifications of Test Rig are as under,

- Stoke length: - 5, 10 & 15 mm.
- Load range: -15 N to 150 N.
- Frequency range: - 5 Hz to 30 Hz, L.C - 0.1 Hz.
- Temperature range: - Ambient to 100°C at Bottom of the sample.
- Frictional Force range: - 400 N (Piezoelectric Sensor C04 make: ICS, L.C- 0.1N, Accuracy-1±1%N).

Friction force measurement of actual segments of ring & liner of 100cc Internal Combustion Engine is considered. Different lubricant used for analysis of friction force and compare them[13],[14],[15]. A computer accomplished data acquisition enabling on-line calculation for the average friction force and coefficient of friction using normal load, over predefine time interval.

4. Result and Discussion:

The co-efficient of friction between the top piston ring and cylinder liner was studied at different lubricant using Reciprocating Friction and Wear Monitor. An Experimental performed with different lubricant at different speed and constant temperature. Fig. 4.1 shown the Effects of Lubricant on Co-efficient of friction: at 40 N Load, and at 40°C temperature and Fig. 4.2 shown the Effects of Lubricant on Co-efficient of friction: at 40 N Load, and at 90°C temperature

Fig. 4.1 Speed v/s Co-efficient of friction at 90°C

Fig. 4.2 Speed v/s Co-efficient of friction at 90°C

Fig. 4.3 Effect of Speed on Co-efficient on Friction

Co-efficient of friction reduces with increase in speed in all three different standard oil. The trend is in line with published work [12]. This indicates that at lower operating speed the fluid film formation not complete. Hence the coefficient of friction occurs between ring-liner is higher. At higher speed co-efficient of friction is less, which shows the formation of full lubrication film between ring-liner specimens at 40°C. Low viscosity oil has offered higher Co-efficient of friction at all speed in comparison to other two oils. Oil B and C performs equally between 600-1200 rpm range. and oil 'B' has offered minimum co-efficient of friction at all rpm, except at 600 rpm little higher value.

At higher operating condition (90°C), the trend is found with similar to 40°C condition. 'B' oil given lower co-efficient of friction compare to other oils at 1500 rpm in all three oil, Fig. 4.3. the co-efficient of friction decreases with increase the reciprocating speed. At 300 rpm the 'A' grade oil has a higher co-efficient of friction compare to 'C' grade oil. At lower speed and high temperature co-efficient of friction observed major different in all the oils. This

may be effect of viscosities of oil at higher temperature and due to viscous force; the co-efficient of friction appears high. During the high speed, co-efficient of friction noted less, this might be full fluid film formulation. 'B' oil has offered minimum co-efficient of friction at all rpm.

5. Conclusion:

The results of the experimental study showed that the use of correct oil affected on co-efficient of friction that is directly affect on the engine performance. Further addition of Oil additive and it's testing will help to reduce friction effect and improve engine performance (Experimental work in process).

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